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Specifications of the Treated Water Processed using Natural Coagulants for its use in Concreting

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ABSTRACT

Wastewater treated using natural coagulants are also achieving greater treatment efficiency similar to the chemical coagulants. Sludge produced by natural coagulants are less in quantity and are mostly biodegradable. Hence, treating wastewater with natural coagulants is an eco-friendly and cost-effective option for the replacement of wastewater treatment using chemical coagulants. Further, the wastewater treated using natural coagulants can be used for various processes. In this study, specifications of the treated water that should meet the certain requirements for using that water in concreting are to be discussed.

Keywords: Concreting, natural coagulants, treated water reuse

INTRODUCTION

Water scarcity has become one of the major concerns in today's world. Treating wastewater is a necessary action to face the water crisis by recycling and reusing it. Treated water can be utilized in construction industry. In concrete, water is required mainly in two stages. One is concrete mixing, and the other one is concrete curing. Water used in these stages must meet the prescribed IS standard specifications to ensure the strength and durability of the concrete. Those specifications of the water and treated water are discussed in this paper.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The treated water must be clean & free of oil, acids, alkalis, salts, sugar, organic materials & other substances that harm the concrete & steel. Potable water is a satisfactory ingredient for concrete mixing & curing.[4]

To neutralize the 100ml acidic nature water, 5ml of 0.02N NaOH need to be sufficient. To neutralize the 100ml alkali nature water, 25ml of 0.02N H₂SO₄ need to be sufficient.

Organic matter presence should not exceed 200mg/l. Inorganic matter presence should not exceed 3000mg/l. Sulphates content should not exceed 400mg/l. Chlorides content should not exceed 2000mg/l for plain concrete. Chlorides content should not exceed 500mg/l for reinforced concrete. Suspended matter should not exceed 2000mg/l.

Initial setting time of the cement should not be less than 30minutes & the IST of

cement mix made with sample water should not have the deviation of ± 30 mins comparing to the controlled cement mix made with distilled water.

28 days compressive strength of the concrete made with sample water should achieve at least 90% of the 28 days average compressive strength of the controlled concrete made with distilled water.

pH value of the water should be 6 to 8.

Sea water is not recommended for concreting in general. On unavoidable situations, it can be used for plain cement concrete after thorough consideration of its disadvantages & precautions.

Treated water which is found satisfactory for concrete mixing can be used for concrete curing also. Moreover, curing water should not create strain/ deposit on the concrete surface. Presence of tannic acid & iron compounds are not acceptable.[7]

METHODOLOGY[8-13]

1. Take the treated water sample
2. Check for cleanliness
3. Measure the acidity and or alkalinity as per IS 3025_Part 22 & Part 23
4. Measure the organic matter as per IS 3025_Part 18
5. Measure the inorganic matter as per IS 3025_Part 18
6. Measure the sulphate content as per IS 3025_Part 24
7. Measure the chloride content as per IS 3025_Part 32
8. Measure the suspended matter as per IS

3025_Part 17

9. Measure Initial Setting Time of Cement made with controlled sample and treated water as per IS 4031_Part 5[5,6]
10. Compare the Initial Setting Time of both the samples
11. Measure the 28 days compressive strength of concrete made with distilled water and treated water as per IS 516[2,3]
12. Compare the compressive strength values achieved by both the samples.
13. Measure the pH of the treated water.
14. If all the results are meeting the specifications mentioned in IS 456, utilize that treated water for concreting otherwise treat again.[1]

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The treated water will be analyzed. All the parameters: acidity, alkalinity, organic matter, inorganic matter, sulphate content, chloride content, suspended matter, Initial setting time of cement, Compressive strength of concrete and pH will be found and cross verified with the specifications of water used for concreting.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the study concludes that the natural coagulants can be used as a best alternative for chemical coagulants in wastewater treatment. Further, the wastewater treated with natural coagulants can be used for various purposes, especially in concreting. The use of treated water processed using natural coagulants in concreting is the best eco-friendly and cost-effecting option.

FUTURE SCOPE

On doing various in-depth studies, the wastewater treated using various natural

coagulants can be used for mass concreting & heavy volume concrete production also with any compromise on quality, strength and durability of the concrete.

REFERENCES

1. IS 456 – Plain and Reinforced concrete – code of practice.
2. IS 516 – Methods of tests for strength of concrete.
3. IS 516_Part 1 – Methods of tests for strength of concrete. Hardened
4. Concrete — Methods of Test Part 1 Testing of Strength of Hardened Concrete
5. Section 1 Compressive, Flexural and Split Tensile Strength.
6. IS 4031– Methods of Physical tests for hydraulic cement Part 5
7. Determination of Initial and Final Setting times.
8. IS 3025 – Methods of Sampling and Test (Physical and Chemical) for Water and Wastewater Part 17 Non-Filterable Residue (Total Suspended Solids at 103°C-105°C)
9. IS 3025 – Methods of Sampling and Test (Physical and Chemical) for Water and Wastewater Part 18 Volatile and Fixed Solids (Total, Filterable and Non- Filterable) at 550°C
10. IS 3025 – Methods of Sampling and Test (Physical and Chemical) for Water and Wastewater Part 22 Acidity
11. IS 3025 - Methods of Sampling and Test (Physical and Chemical) for Water and Wastewater Part 23 Alkalinity
12. IS 3025 - Methods of Sampling and Test (Physical and Chemical)

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24 Sulphates
13. IS 3025 - Methods of Sampling
and Test (Physical and Chemical)
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Chloride.